

THE PHRASEOLOGICAL ISSUES OF FIRE SAFETY TERMINOLOGY AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Abstract. This article discusses the phraseological issues of fire safety terminology and their significance in the translation process. The author emphasizes the importance of correct translation of fire safety terms, especially their alignment with international standards, for technical and legal specialists. The article highlights the significance of correctly interpreting certain metaphorical expressions and considering semantic differences. One of the main issues addressed is the necessity of a proper contextual approach to avoid misinterpretation in the literal translation of fire safety terms, such as firestorm, backdraft, and fire suppression system.

Keywords: Fire safety, terminology, phraseology, translation process, equivalence, metaphor, technical terms, international standards, semantic differences.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yong'in xavfsizligi terminologiyasining frazeologik muammolari va ularning tarjima jarayonidagi ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Yong'in xavfsizligi bo'yicha texnik va yuridik mutaxassislar uchun muhim bo'lgan terminlarning to'g'ri tarjima qilinishi, ayniqsa, xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirilishi zarurligini ta'kidlanadi. Maqolada, ayrim metaforik iboralarning aniq talqin qilinishi va semantik tafovutlarni hisobga olishning ahamiyati alohida ko'rsatilgan. Asosiy masalalardan biri, yong'in xavfsizligi sohasidagi terminlar, xususan, 'firestorm', 'backdraft', 'fire suppression system' kabi iboralar, so'zma-so'z tarjimalarida noto'g'ri tushunilmasligi uchun, to'g'ri kontekstual yondashuvning zarurligi hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yong'in xavfsizligi, terminologiya, frazeologiya, tarjima jarayoni, ekvivalentlik, metafora, texnik terminlar, xalqaro standartlar, semantik tafovutlar.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются фразеологические проблемы терминологии противопожарной безопасности и их значение в процессе перевода. Автор подчеркивает важность правильного перевода терминов противопожарной безопасности, особенно их соответствия международным стандартам, для технических и юридических специалистов. В статье выделяется важность правильной интерпретации определенных метафорических выражений и учета семантических различий. Одной из главных проблем, поднятых в статье, является необходимость правильного контекстуального подхода для предотвращения неправильной интерпретации при дословном переводе терминов противопожарной безопасности, таких как firestorm, backdraft и fire suppression system.

Ключевые слова: Противопожарная безопасность, терминология, фразеология, процесс перевода, эквивалентность, метафора, технические термины, международные стандарты, семантические различия.

Introduction.

Fire safety terminology is crucial for every specialist, as the accurate interpretation of these terms is vital not only for technical professionals but also for those dealing with legal

documents. For translators, it is important to correctly translate these terms, as any ambiguity or mistranslation can lead to unforeseen consequences. In particular, technical terms in the field of fire safety must be expressed accurately and correctly in international communication and legal documents. The proper interpretation of fire safety terminology is essential not only for technical specialists but also for professionals working with legal documents. Misinterpretations or mistakes in translation can lead to significant losses in real-life situations. Some terms need to be provided in a form that corresponds to international standards to preserve their meaning. In some cases, when no direct equivalent can be found, an explanatory approach should be used. Certain expressions have metaphorical meanings, and their correct interpretation is of particular importance in the terminology field. For instance, the term *firestorm* refers not just to a regular fire but to a rapidly spreading and highly dangerous fire. Translating it literally as *firestorm* may lead to confusion, so it is more accurate to explain it as a *rapidly expanding strong fire*. Another important technical term is *backdraft*, which refers to a situation where a fire inside, due to a lack of oxygen, smolders, and suddenly an oxygen flow causes an explosion. If this term is incorrectly translated, it could be interpreted as the regular spread of fire. Therefore, it is recommended to explain it as an *explosion that occurs when oxygen reaches the fire*.

These terms, of course, are used synonymously in English fire safety technical literature, but they do not fully correspond to one another. This can be evidenced by the definitions in the dictionary published by the British Standards Institute. In this dictionary, the lemma *fire* is expressed through the term *combustion*, which represents a narrower concept of fire, interpreted as a type of burning process.[1] Another issue in translating fire-technical texts is the interconnection of language units. According to V.N. Komissarov's equivalence theory, the maximum correspondence between the source and target text is achieved through the alignment of five levels of equivalence. However, it is possible for a translation to ensure cross-linguistic communication even if only one of these levels aligns.[2] The meanings of some terms and their translation differences are crucial in fire safety terminology. For example, in English-Russian dictionaries, the term *fire* is translated as *flame*, *fire*, or *blaze*, while *combustion* is translated as *burning*, *scorching*, or *ignition*. Although the meanings of these terms are clearly distinct, they might be used synonymously in the translation process. However, in the terminological glossary published by the U.S. National Fire Protection Association (NFPA), the term *fire* has a much broader definition: it is a rapid oxidation process that generates light and heat through a chemical reaction. These differences illustrate the necessity of maintaining equivalence in translation and avoiding ambiguity.[3] The demand for fire safety specialists continues to grow, as preventing fires is more efficient than extinguishing them. Specialists in this field are increasingly needed in control and monitoring departments, forensic expertise centers, and industrial enterprises to engage in fire prevention, fire-technical expertise, emergency exit planning, and protection system design. Moreover, fire safety professionals often collaborate with foreign companies. In such communication, it is essential to accurately translate specialized fire safety terms. Every term has specific phraseological features, and the translation process requires considering synonymic differences, contextual variations, and semantic subtleties.[4] In modern terminology research, professional terminology occupies a special place. Fire safety terminology and phraseological issues remain highly relevant due to the rapid development of this field and the increasing complexity of technical language. Identifying these terminological features is crucial not only for ensuring accuracy in the translation process but also for enhancing the effectiveness of professional communication.[5] Each country has its own legal norms regarding fire safety. Therefore, when translating legal terms, it is necessary to choose the variant that corresponds not

only linguistically but also legally. For example, the term *fire warden* used in the United States may refer to a position that does not exist in some countries. Translating this term directly as *fire guard* might be incorrect, as the role is concerned with checking and managing safety measures before a fire occurs. Thus, it would be more accurate to translate it as *responsible person for fire safety*.

The names of technical devices also require special attention during translation. For example, the term *fire suppression system* might be translated as *fire extinguishing system*, but this might not be fully understood, as it refers not only to systems that extinguish fires with water or foam but also to automatic fire detection and suppression mechanisms. Therefore, it should be translated as *automatic fire detection and suppression system*. Sometimes expressions referring to technical processes need to be properly explained. For example, the term *flash point* refers to the flammability of liquids, and translating it as *ignition temperature* would be incorrect because it denotes the minimum temperature at which a liquid can produce flammable vapors. It is more accurate to explain it as *the minimum temperature at which flammable vapors are released*.

Another important term is *fire lane*, which should not be simply translated as *fire road*. This term refers to a lane designated for fire trucks and emergency services to quickly reach the scene of a fire. Therefore, it should be translated as *fire lane for emergency services*. The translation process must also take into account various cultural and technical differences. For example, while in some countries, *fire safety drill* refers to practical training conducted regularly, in others, it may be based on theoretical preparation. Hence, it would be appropriate to translate it as *fire safety training* or *fire preparedness exercises*. Accurate translation of phraseological units helps to avoid misunderstandings in fire safety. Each unit has a specific meaning, and incorrect translation can alter its essence. Translators must interpret these terms correctly not only from a linguistic standpoint but also within the framework of technical and legal contexts. Additionally, working with international standards and norms enhances translation quality. The accurate translation of fire safety terms contributes to improving fire prevention measures, enhancing emergency preparedness, and preventing misunderstandings on an international scale. Therefore, translators need to possess technical knowledge, deeply understand legal norms, and be aware of the subtleties of phraseological units.

Conclusion: The correct interpretation of phraseological units in the translation of fire safety terminology is crucial not only linguistically but also from technical and legal perspectives. To prevent ambiguities, fire safety specialists and translators must adopt methods that align with international standards.

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